

The performance of international cut-off values for anthropometric obesity measures in predicting hypertension and diabetes in Nigerians: a systematic review and bayesian meta-analysis

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Abstract

Background: Body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), and waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) have all been used as screening methods to predict cardiometabolic disorders. However, different racial and ethnic groupings have distinct cut-off levels for predicting a wide range of cardiometabolic disorders. This study aimed to assess how well these risk indicators predict diabetes and hypertension among Nigerians.

Methods: Google Scholar, PubMed, and Scopus online databases were searched from December 2021 to June 2022, with studies selected based on predetermined criteria. Meta-analysis was carried out on 55 papers with a total sample size of 43,290.

Results: Using BMI to predict hypertension has a pooled sensitivity of 49% (95% CI: 41-57%) and specificity of 69% (95% CI: 62-75%), while the comparable results for predicting diabetes were 56% (95% CI: 38-72%) and 67% (95% CI: 19-94%). WC predicts hypertension with a pooled sensitivity of 41% (95% CI: 25-60%) and specificity of 68% (95% CI: 48-82%). Using WHR to predict hypertension has a pooled sensitivity of 65% (95% CI: 21-91%) and specificity of 50% (95% CI: 16-84%); for predicting diabetes, the equivalent results were 76% (95% CI: 33-94%) and 57% (95% CI: 20-86%). The areas under the receiver operating characteristics curve for all parameters were consistently less than 40%.

Conclusion: When worldwide cut-off values are utilized, BMI and WC perform badly, however WHR performs fairly well as screening instruments for diabetes and hypertension in Nigeria.

Keywords: Body mass index, Waist-circumference, Waist-to-hip ratio, Cut-off values, ROC curve, Hypertension, Diabetes, Nigeria

Introduction

Cardiometabolic risk has been linked to body mass index (BMI) (1), waist circumference (WC), waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), and waist-to-height ratio (WHtR) (2-5). As a result, anthropometric measurements of generalized and central obesity have been employed as

low-cost, easily accessible, and simple screening tools for cardiovascular disease and diabetes (2,6,7). The diagnostic performance of such anthropometric characteristics in this response can be evaluated using sensitivity, specificity, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (8).

It has also been established that different racial and ethnic groups have varied ideal anthropometric cut-off values, resulting in different sensitivities, specificities, and AUCs for predicting a variety of cardiometabolic illnesses (1,2,6). As a result, it has been suggested that race and ethnicity-specific anthropometric cutoff values be employed to estimate cardiometabolic risk (1, 2, 6).

Globally, BMI is defined as the range of 18.50-24.99 kg/m². Values less than 18.50 kg/m² were considered underweight, whereas values of 25.0 kg/m² or beyond were considered abnormal (9). There are four (four) types of abnormal BMI: preobesity and classes I-III of obesity. The categories' ranges are 25-29.99 kg/m², 30-34.99 kg/m², 35-39.99 kg/m², and 40 kg/m² or above (9). The World Health Organization defined sex-specific central obesity as a waist-hip ratio of more than 0.9 in men and more than 0.85 in women (2). The body also recommended ethnic-specific cut offs of WC for defining central obesity, such as values of ≥ 94 cm and ≥ 102 cm for increased and significantly increased cardiovascular risks for Caucasian males, and corresponding values for females of ≥ 80 cm and ≥ 88 cm, respectively (2).

In Africa, the best cut-off point for BMI was discovered to be 22 kg/m² for men and 28 kg/m² for women for black South Africans (10), and 22.2 kg/m² for males and 24.5 kg/m² for females for Ethiopians (11). An analysis of individual level cross-sectional data on 24 181 participants aged ≥ 15 years from 17 studies conducted between 1990 and 2014 in eight countries in Sub-Saharan Africa revealed that the optimal WC cut-point for identifying men at increased cardiometabolic risk is lower (≥ 81.2 cm) than the international value (≥ 94.0 cm) and similar to that in women (12).

The appropriate BMI cut-off for men and women in Nigeria has been reported to be 24.1 kg/m² and 28.9 kg/m², respectively (13). Another study of 5135 participants aged ≥ 16 years in the country indicated that the best WC cut-off value was 85cm for males and 91cm for females (14).

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic review and meta-analysis to evaluate the efficacy of international anthropometric cut-off values in predicting cardiometabolic risk in Nigeria. We intend to assess the efficacy of international cut-off values for anthropometric obesity measures in predicting hypertension and diabetes among Nigerians.

Methodology

Study area

Nigeria is a lower middle-income Western African country with a land area of 923,769 square kilometers and over 250 ethnic groups (16). It consists of 36 states

and a capital divided into six geopolitical zones or regions, three in each of the northern and southern portions of the country. The estimated population for 2021 was 211.4 million, with 43.4% of the population under the age of 14, 53.9% between the ages of 15 and 64, and only 2.8% over the age of 65 (17).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

This review included community- and hospital-based studies conducted in apparently healthy Nigerians aged > 18 years from 2000 to 2021. The studies used international cut off values for defining obesity (i.e., BMI values of 25.0 kg/m² and above are defined as abnormal (9) and central obesity as WC ≥ 94 cm for males and ≥ 80 cm for females or WHR ≥ 0.9 for males and ≥ 0.85 for females (14)) and reported hypertension, diabetes, and dyslipidemia as target conditions. This review excluded case-control studies, studies conducted on people with chronic medical disorders, and studies conducted on pregnant women and children. This study also excluded studies that did not give measurements of sensitivity and specificity of anthropometric characteristics and did not provide data to allow for their computation.

Search strategies

The online databases used were Google Scholar, PubMed, and Scopus. The following search terms and phrases were used: WC, central obesity, central adiposity, abdominal obesity, BMI, WHR, and generalized obesity. The search was repeated for each word or phrase containing the terms "diabetes," "hypertension," "sensitivity," "specificity," "area under the curve," and the name "Nigeria." The search was held from December 2021 to June 2022. Two reviewers separately screened the abstracts and titles of the papers, and studies were selected and excluded in accordance with predetermined criteria. An effort was made to include all available studies, including a search for references in the included studies. The full-text publications were then screened independently by the same researchers to select the studies for inclusion in qualitative and quantitative analyses.

Quality appraisal of the included studies

The studies were assessed using the QUADAS-2 tool (18). This instrument has four domains: patient selection, index tests, reference standards, and flow and timing. Each domain is appraised for bias risk, and the first three domains are also evaluated for applicability concerns (18). The guidelines created expressly for this review were as follows:

- i. Any 'No' answer to any of the signaling questions in the three domains of "patient selection", "index test", and "reference

- ii. standard" should result in a judgment of "high risk of bias" or "high risk of concern for applicability" for that domain. Two (two) "No" responses to signaling questions are required for the risk of bias domains of "flow" and "timing" to result in a "high risk of bias" evaluation.
- iii. Any study that received a judgment of "high risk of bias" or "high risk of concern for applicability" in any of the three domains of "patient selection," "index test," or "reference standard" would receive an overall judgment of "high risk of bias" or "high risk of concern for applicability," as applicable.
- iv. Any study that received an overall rating of "high risk of bias" or "high risk of concern for applicability" will be omitted from the quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis).

The flow method of article search, retrieval, and analysis was depicted diagrammatically using the PRISMA2020 web tool (19).

Data extraction and quantitative analysis

Two reviewers (MAB and MM) extracted the data independently. The number of true positives and true negatives, the number of people with the target conditions (hypertension and diabetes), and the number of people who are disease-free were among the data extracted from the investigations. The study also collected the sample size, cut off values for the anthropometric measures, and mean age of the individuals.

All analyses were carried out using R statistical environment version 4.1.2 (20). A Bayesian meta-analysis of diagnostic test data was performed using the R-package bamdit (21) that employs a bivariate random effects model, which models the number of true positives and false positives using two conditional binomial distributions and a bivariate normal distribution for the random effects. Pooled sensitivity, specificity, and area under the curve were reported for each anthropometric measure and target condition, along with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI).

Results

Search results

Out of the 19307 studies collected, 70 were used in the qualitative analysis and 55 in the quantitative synthesis (Figure 1).

Risk of bias and applicability concerns assessment of the included studies

Out of the 70 studies included in the qualitative analysis, 15 (approximately one-fifth) had a high risk of bias or applicability problems, therefore they were eliminated from the quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) (Figure 2 and table 2).

Characteristics of the studies included in the quantitative analysis

The 55 papers considered in the quantitative synthesis have a total sample size of 43290. As shown in Figure 3, seventy (70) estimates of sensitivity and specificity for BMI were reported, with the target condition being hypertension in 40 estimates, diabetes mellitus in 9 estimates, raised total cholesterol in 6 estimates, raised triglycerides in 5 estimates, low HDL cholesterol in 5 estimates, raised LDL cholesterol in 4 estimates, and combined dyslipidemia in one estimate.

There were 12 estimates of sensitivity and specificity for WC and 7 estimates for WHR, both with hypertension as the target condition (Figure 3).

Diagnostic performance of BMI

In Nigeria, BMI has a pooled sensitivity of 49% and specificity of 69% for predicting hypertension (Table 1), and 56% and specificity of 67% for predicting diabetes (Table 1). The confidence interval for the sensitivity but not the specificity estimations was 50%. The pooled areas under the curve for BMI pooled sensitivity and specificity for diabetes and hypertension were 41% and 40%, respectively (Figures 4 and 5).

Diagnostic performance of WC and WHR

WC has a pooled sensitivity of 41% and specificity of 68% in predicting hypertension in Nigeria (Table 1). The pooled area under the curve was 38% (Figure 5).

The WHR has a pooled sensitivity of 65% and specificity of 50% for predicting hypertension (Table 1), and a pooled sensitivity of 76% and specificity of 57% for predicting diabetes in Nigeria (Table 1). The WHR's pooled sensitivity and specificity for predicting diabetes and hypertension were 38% and 36%, respectively (Figures 4 and 5).

Table 1. Performance of BMI, WHR and WC in Predicting Hypertension and Diabetes

Parameter	Hypertension			Diabetes		
	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	AUC (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	AUC (%)
BMI	49 (41-57)	69 (62-75)	40 (36-40)	56 (38-72%)	67 (19-94)	41 (33-47)
WC	41 (25-60)	68 (48-82)	38 (25-42)			
WHR	65 (21-91)	50 (16-84)	36 (27-44)	76 (33-94)	57 (20-86)	38 (17-62)

BMI = body mass index, WC = waist circumference, WHR = waist-to-hip ratio, AUC = area under the curve. Values in brackets are 95% Credible Intervals

Table 2. Quality Appraisal of the Included Studies

Reference number	Overall Risk of bias	Overall applicability	Quality	Sample size	Settlement	Setting	Measure	Target condition
22	Low	Low	Good	3211	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI	HDL-C, LDL-C, TC & TG
23	Low	Low	Good	2807	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI, WC & WHR	HTN
24	Low	Low	Good	400	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
25	Low	Low	Good	775	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
26	Low	Low	Good	782	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
27	High	High	Poor	845	Rural	Population-based	BMI	DM & HTN
28	High	Low	Poor	750	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
29	Low	Low	Good	324	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
30	Low	Low	Good	566	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI, WC & WHR	HTN
31	High	Low	Poor	147	Rural	Population-based	BMI, WC & WHR	DM
32	Low	Low	Good	381	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
33	Low	Low	Good	1265	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
34	Low	Low	Good	447	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI & WC	TG
35	High	High	Poor	398	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WHR	HTN
36	Low	Low	Good	912	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
37	Low	Low	Good	445	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
38	High	Low	Poor	462	Rural	Population-based	BMI & WHR	DM
39	Low	Low	Good	257	Rural	Population-based	WC	HTN & Combined Dyslipidemia
40	Low	Low	Good	750	Rural	Population-based	BMI & WHR	DM
41	High	Low	Poor	300	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN

Cut-off values for obesity measures to predict hypertension and diabetes

42	Low	Low	Good	325	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI	HDL-C, LDL-C, TC & TG
43	High	High	Poor	300	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
44	Low	Low	Good	6915	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
45	Low	Low	Good	242	Urban	Population-based	BMI	DM
46	Low	Low	Good	354	Rural	Population-based	BMI & WHR	HTN
47	Low	Low	Good	138	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI	HDL-C, LDL-C, TC & TG
48	Low	Low	Good	360	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
49	Low	Low	Good	491	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WHR	DM
50	High	Low	Poor	184	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
51	Low	Low	Good	324	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
52	Low	Low	Good	4088	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
53	Low	High	Poor	6766	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
54	Low	Low	Good	229	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WC	TC
55	Low	High	Poor	112	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
56	Low	Low	Good	482	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI & WHR	HTN
57	Low	Low	Good	191	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
58	Low	Low	Good	231	Urban	Population-based	WC	HTN
59	Low	Low	Good	199	Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN
60	Low	Low	Good	1012	Rural	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
61	Low	Low	Good	866	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN
62	Low	Low	Good	367	Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN
63	Low	Low	Good	181	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
64	Low	Low	Good	271	Urban	Population-based	BMI	DM & HTN
65	Low	Low	Good	412	Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN
66	High	High	Poor	13591		Population-based		
67	High	High	Poor	320	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
68	Low	Low	Good	259	Rural	Population-based	BMI	DM, HDL-C, HTN & TC
69	Low	Low	Good	163	Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN
70	Low	Low	Good	400	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
71	Low	Low	Good	231	Urban	Population-based	BMI, WC & WHR	HTN
72	Low	Low	Good	244	Urban	Population-based	BMI, WC, WHR & WHtR	HTN

73	Low	Low	Good	3780	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
74	Low	Low	Good	1610	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
75	Low	Low	Good	294	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
76	Low	Low	Good	480	Urban	Hospital-based	BMI	DM
77	Low	Low	Good	400	Urban	Population-based	BMI	Combined Dyslipidemia
78	Low	Low	Good	806	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
79	Low	High	Poor	497	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
80	Low	Low	Good	325	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HDL-C, LDL-C, TC & TG
81	Low	Low	Good	912	Urban & Rural	Population-based	BMI & WHR	HTN
82	Low	Low	Good	500	Rural	Population-based	BMI & WC	HTN
83	Low	Low	Good	436	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
84	Low	Low	Good	964	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
85	Low	Low	Good	411	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
86	Low	Low	Good	280	Urban	Population-based	BMI	DM
87	Low	Low	Good	232	Urban	Population-based	BMI & WHtR	HTN
88	Low	Low	Good	300	Urban	Population-based	BMI	DM & HTN
89	Low	Low	Good	872	Urban	Population-based	BMI	HTN
90	Low	High	Poor	308	Urban	Population-based	BMI	DM & HTN
91	Low	Low	Good	451	Rural	Population-based	BMI	HTN

HTN = hypertension, DM = diabetes, BMI = body mass index, WC = waist circumference, WHR = waist-to-hip ratio, WHtR = waist to height ratio, HDL-C = high density lipoprotein cholesterol, LDL-C = low density lipoprotein cholesterol, TC = total cholesterol & TG = triglycerides

Figure 1. Results of the Search of Studies for Systematic Review of Diagnostic Performance of Anthropometric Parameters

Figure 2. Risk of Bias (Plot A) and Applicability Concerns (plot B) Assessment of the Included Studies

Figure 3. Reported Anthropometric Parameters and the Corresponding Target Conditions

Figure 4. The Summary ROC Curve of Body Mass Index (plot A) and Waist-to-Hip Ratio (plot B) for Predicting Diabetes

Figure 5. The Summary ROC Curve of Body Mass Index (plot A) and Waist Circumference (plot B) for Predicting Hypertension.

Discussion

BMI and WC were discovered to have low pooled true positive rates (sensitivity) and low pooled false negative rates (specificity) for predicting hypertension in Nigerians. BMI exhibited the same low true positive and false negative rates in predicting diabetes across the country. These statistics imply that when employed as screening methods, BMI and WC will fail to identify many hypertensive and diabetic individuals. This makes BMI and WC ineffective screening measures for many disorders. The implication is that many Nigerians with hypertension and diabetes will be classed as having a normal BMI and/or WC. In contrast, the WHR was found to have a high pooled true positive rate for predicting both diabetes and hypertension. This makes WHR an effective screening tool for cardiometabolic disorders in Nigerians. The Summary Receiver Operating Characteristic (SROC) curves for all three anthropometric measurements of adiposity (BMI, WC, and WHR) had a low pooled area under the curve (AUC). This suggests that the three obesity measures have weak discriminant properties for diabetes and hypertension among Nigerians.

This study's poor true positive rates of predicting hypertension using BMI or WC are consistent with 48.1% among Indian adult males (92) and 38.2% among women in the Asia Pacific region (93). The meta-analysis indicated that BMI has a greater specificity than sensitivity in predicting diabetes, which was also documented among Iranian adults (94). The meta-analysis indicated that WHR has relatively high true positive rates and low true negative rates in predicting hypertension and diabetes, which is comparable with what has been reported among Portuguese (95), Iranian (94) and Turkish (96) adults. The increased sensitivity of WHR compared to BMI is another evidence of central adiposity's well-known higher cardiometabolic risk than broad obesity (3-5).

BMI or WC have relatively low true positive rates and high true negative rates in predicting hypertension and diabetes, although both obesity measures had better sensitivity and specificity among Portuguese (93), Iranian (92), Turkish (96) and African American people (97). The sensitivity of WHR discovered in this meta-analysis is greater than the 59.5% reported among Turkish adults (96) and the 61% reported among African Americans (97).

The area under the curve for BMI, WC, and WHR is less than 50%, indicating that these anthropometric measurements of obesity have low discriminatory potential among Nigerians in terms of hypertension and diabetes. This is in contrast to the findings of Indians

(BMI & WC AUC > 78% for predicting hypertension) (92), Iranians (94), Malaysians (93), Northern Americans (94), Portuguese (95), and Japanese (95). Furthermore, contrary to the findings of this meta-analysis, a meta-analysis of global studies found BMI and WC ROC AUCs of 69% and 72%, respectively, for predicting hypertension (96). A more recent meta-analysis reported ROC AUCs of 66% and 69% (97). One possible explanation for this mismatch is because the studies included in this meta-analysis employed BMI and WC cut-off points intended for European populations; such cut-off values may not represent increased adiposity or cardiovascular risk among Nigerians.

This meta-analysis has several strengths. First, we used a common quality assessment tool (QUADAS-2) to exclude studies with high risk or bias from the quantitative synthesis. Second, the bamdit R tool used in the research used heavy-tailed distributions, so outlier studies had no meaningful effect on the final pooled values. However, the study is not without flaws. Excluding case-control studies and those done on people with chronic medical issues eliminates a huge number of papers from the meta-analysis. This has impacted the precision of the sensitivity, specificity, and ROC AUC values, as indicated by the large 95% credible ranges. Second, this meta-analysis did not examine the performance of anthropometric measurements of obesity in predicting cardiometabolic diseases such as metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia, stroke, chronic renal disease, or cardiovascular mortality. The diagnostic efficacy of anthropometric measures of obesity will undoubtedly be influenced by how effectively they predict additional cardiometabolic disorders, in addition to diabetes and hypertension.

Conclusion and recommendations

When international cutoff values are utilized, BMI and WC are poor screening tools, whereas WHR is an adequate screening tool for diabetes and hypertension. All three obesity measures were found to have poor discriminant capacity for hypertension and diabetes among Nigerians. Further meta-analyses are needed to determine how effectively these obesity indicators predict other cardiometabolic diseases and mortality. It is advised that large-scale population-based and longitudinal studies be conducted to determine the best cut-off values for BMI and central obesity measurements in predicting cardiometabolic risk in Nigeria.

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